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CHAMPION Project Newsletter

Issue 3, January 2022

CHAMPION consortium reaches milestone in safe and circular material development

Researchers of the CHAMPION project have successfully prepared a first set of innovative bio-based materials with promising properties for coatings, adhesives and home care ingredients.

CHAMPION sets out to develop mild methods to convert safe-by-design bio-based chemical building blocks into novel polymeric materials. The selected chemistry to achieve this is called aza-Michael addition. This chemistry is fast even at room temperature, and it is very atom-efficient; no co-products are liberated during polymerisation ('click chemistry'). Unlike well-known industrial click polymerisation systems such as those based on isocyanates and epoxides, the polymerisation technology targeted in CHAMPION stays away from toxic and unsustainable ingredients, by discarding chemicals and materials that receive unfavourable scores in toxicity assessments. In addition, the consortium prioritises only those aza-Michael polymer

Evaluation of material performance is an integral part of the project. Applications of interest for the consortium's industrial end-users range from flexible and rigid coatings and structural adhesives to water-soluble home-care ingredients. For coatings and adhesives, an important requirement is sufficient hardness of the product. In initial screenings of aza-Michael polymerizations on lab-scale, this proved to be challenging; most of the cured products were relatively soft rubber-like materials. However, the CHAMPION team is happy to announce that they have now been able to demonstrate that, by shifting to ingredients able to provide a more densely cross-linked polymer network, materials with good hardness could be prepared. The formulations will now be further evaluated by participating industrial end-users.

polymers with novel bio-based polymers for their application in coatings, textiles, home care uses and structural adhesives. But views on what sustainability means exactly, vary widely. Project partners nova-Institute and SQ Consult defined a strategy in which sustainability guides the decision-making process for selecting suitable CHAMPION polymers.

The main aim of the sustainability assessment within the project is to guide the process development. The strategy starts with a checklist summarizing important sustainability aspects for the synthesis and processing of polymers. These aspects, including common principles of green chemistry, have to be taken into consideration by project partners during the first steps of development. In the next step, quantitative indicators are gathered in a techno-economic evaluation (TEE) – how much it would cost - and the life cycle assessment (LCA) of selected candidates – what the environmental impact would be. These indicators include for example the economics, greenhouse gas emissions, and biomass utilisation efficiency. This initial assessment results in a further selection of suitable polymers and additionally in the identification of key factors potentially influencing sustainability once their development reaches a higher maturity level. Examples of such factors include establishing feedstock suppliers, determining target applications, establishing a commercially viable production, and consumer acceptance. Assessment results will then be used to identify which project partners and stakeholders should come together to address potential challenges. For example, by identifying opportunities to establish appropriate supply chains for new materials, to contribute to market uptake and consumer acceptance and to support other activities from the project on policy recommendations, regulatory framework, eco-labelling possibilities, etc.

At the end of the project, a detailed sustainability assessment of the most promising CHAMPION polymers will be carried out following a set of criteria covering the three pillars of sustainability. The selection of criteria follows various acknowledged standards and methodologies such as the EN 16751:2016, VDI 4605 and takes into account key circularity indicators. The detailed assessment provides key points to follow for a comprehensive analysis: various areas are supported by quantitative indicators provided within the project and other areas require a more qualitative analysis.

Moreover, the assessment will present some discussions and recommendations describing all actions undertaken in the project pursuing sustainability. It will also identify potential problems that may arise in future process development and suggest recommendations wherever possible.

Several CHAMPION activities support the sustainability goals directly during the project, including replacing fossil-based starting materials with bio-based ones and targeting circular polymers. Nevertheless, sustainability is highly dependent on establishing appropriate supply chains for sustainable input materials, so that it is possible to meet future demand, once CHAMPION polymers reach a higher maturity level. This strategy aspires to reflect this complex multi-criteria analysis by tackling sustainability from the beginning of the development

Upcoming EU regulation for bio-based products

The CHAMPION project is developing novel bio-based polymers that are circular by design, i.e. recyclable back to bio-based monomers, and/or biodegradable. Just as polymers from fossil origin, these bio-based polymers need to comply with various EU regulations for their end-of-life options. However, there is currently no comprehensive EU law in place applying to bio-based, biodegradable and compostable polymers or products. Part of this regulatory gap is currently being addressed.

The most prominent current EU regulation for the end-of life options on the European market includes the following:

Regulation	Main Requirement	Specific info for biopolymers
Waste Framework Directive	Loss of material after a product's service life should be prevented and further processing and handling of waste is required, following the waste hierarchy. Provisions apply regardless of material origin and regardless of its degradability profile.	Biopolymers produced from biowaste within the meaning of the WFD could obtain an End-of-Waste (EoW) status and only then regulations for further processing and handling do no longer have to be followed.
EU standards for industrial composting and bio-degradation	Requirements on disintegration and biodegradation of products. Example: standard EN 13432 requires for packaging at least 90% disintegration after 12 weeks and 90% biodegradation in 6 months.	Also applies to bio-based products
Single Use Plastics Directive and its rules for application	Depending on existence of suitable alternatives, placing single-use plastics or plastic materials on the market is prohibited or the use of such plastics should be reduced.	The provisions also apply to plastics manufactured from biobased materials or biodegradable plastics.

Current regulation focuses on packaging and plastics. In this smaller scope, no harmonized standards yet exist for marine degradability of plastics. The [European Chemicals Agency](#) has proposed an EU-wide restriction on products placed on the EU/EEA market that contain intentionally added microplastics. This restriction is to be added under the EU's chemicals legislation [REACH](#). Also currently no specific standards and guidelines exist on design-for-recycling of plastic products. Proposals to address this gap have been made by the European Commission's

The applicability of bio-based polymers will be further impacted by wider regulation currently being developed by the European Commission. The policy framework on the sourcing, labelling and use of bio-based plastics, and the use of biodegradable and compostable plastics was announced in both the [European Green Deal](#) and the [New Circular Economy Action Plan](#), with a [planned](#) launch in 2021. Although this timeline was not achieved, it is now expected soon. Details will be shared in the next CHAMPION newsletter.

The CHAMPION External Advisory Board

The CHAMPION External Advisory Board (EAB) is a key element in steering the project direction and ensuring a high-quality value of project results. The EAB members bring a wide range of expertise and experience in areas relevant to the project including resins and coatings, circular economy, sustainability, policy and composite materials. Two first members of the EAB were included in the [previous newsletter](#). Four further members are introduced in this issue.

Beene N'membe is an advanced technologist at the Aerospace Technology Institute (ATI). The ATI works with the wider aerospace industry to develop UK capabilities in strategic technologies via building consortia, chairing working groups, developing roadmaps and assessing innovative industry project proposals for UK government funds. The ATI also defines the UK aerospace technology strategy. Beene works in the structures, materials and manufacturing team, where she leads on composite materials, tooling and modelling and simulation.

Michiel van Kuppevelt is a circular economy policy advisor at the Dutch Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM). He trained as a Materials Scientist, has experience in industry (R&D) in that field and is also interested in the social sciences combined with technological challenges. He is involved in a diversity of projects and programmes mostly relating to safety, sustainability and circularity. For example, an integrated assessment method between these three topics is being developed, as well as projects on Safe-(and Sustainable)-by-Design (both EU and NL) and on sustainable (use of) plastics.

Ben Greatrex is based at the University of New England in Australia. He is an expert in the derivatization of small molecules and has extensive experience working with the LGO platform. His group has developed a series of transformations for LGO, thus will be able to review and provide insights into the LGO scaffold and other small molecules that are potential building blocks in the CHAMPION project.

Wolfgang Paulus is a senior principal scientist working at BASF. His current role covers challenges and innovations within the field of industrial coating raw materials with a mid- and long-term perspective. This includes evaluation of new crosslinker and binder chemistries within and outside of BASF. In recent years, his focus shifted to more sustainable solutions based on renewable and/or recycled raw materials. He is involved in activities which enable the circular use of coated materials.

Find out more on our website: www.champion-project.eu

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This project has received funding from the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 887398. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio Based Industries Consortium.

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